

Canadian PID Strategy: Vision, Mission, and Principles

Vision

Comprehensive persistent identifier (PID) adoption will underpin an effective and equitable digital research information landscape in Canada, enabling open and persistent connections between research inputs, activities, outputs, and outcomes.

Mission

Recognizing that persistent identifiers are a foundation of a modern digital research system, the national PID strategy will provide a framework to support the widespread adoption of persistent identifiers across the whole Canadian research ecosystem. It will reflect the priorities of all research communities in Canada, recognizing that research takes place within and across different cultures, disciplines, and languages. It will be responsive, equitable, and inclusive, with transparent and consultative processes at its core. The strategy will be built on evidence – from analyzing community needs to evaluating its effectiveness – adapting and evolving over time to ensure technical, organizational, and social sustainability. It will be nationally focused but internationally networked, incorporating best practice wherever it may be found in order to support the use of PIDs to: uniquely identify a range of entities across the research lifecycle; support interoperability between systems and information resources; and improve the flow of accurate (meta)data.

Principles

These six principles have been developed in response to community consultation undertaken during 2022 and 2023. They are designed to act as a guide to the development and execution of the Canadian national PID strategy, to help to shape decision-making, and to keep the strategy focused on community needs and priorities as it evolves in the future.

1. Open systems will be prioritized wherever feasible

Part of what makes PIDs so valuable is their ability to connect information in different systems and between organizations. Using PIDs, metadata, and registries as bridges between information systems requires maximum access to these tools and minimal limits on data reuse. We will therefore prioritize systems that provide open Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), permissive and clear licensing for data access and use, and that have community governance to assure openness in the future.

2. The strategy, the activities it shapes, and their outcomes must be inclusive and equitable

The benefits of the PID strategy must reach every community engaged in research in Canada. Acknowledging that the value of PIDs grows the more they are used, we will strive to ensure that the value generated by PID adoption is not concentrated on those groups and organizations that already enjoy relative advantages of wealth and status. In practice, this means identifying less advantaged stakeholders, and actively working to secure resources, providing additional support or services, and creating accessible toolkits for those who need them.

3. Community engagement and collaboration will be a central component of the strategy

Our strategy has emerged from community consultations and research. We will ensure that this community-centric approach continues to evolve, proactively fostering collaboration and facilitation across stakeholder groups, including those outside of the existing PID community, in order to understand and amplify their needs. We will raise awareness of PIDs and their benefits among all those contributing to research in Canada through outreach efforts designed to engage, explain, and educate.

4. The national strategy will be international in scope

We recognize that Canadian research activity does not only take place within our borders. Canadian researchers work with collaborators around the globe, receive funding from bodies based outside Canada, and publish in venues managed in other countries. We will be an active voice for our nation among this international network of partnerships, and will prioritize internationally used PIDs, schemas, and infrastructures to ensure that national and international systems can interoperate and share information about research activities, wherever they take place.

5. The goal of the strategy is effective, tangible change

The adoption and integration of PIDs in the tools and systems used every day by researchers and those who support them requires investment and adaptation. These tools and systems must deliver real value, freeing researchers to be more effective by improving discovery, making their working lives easier, and reducing administrative effort. In concrete terms, every intervention proposed in the strategy will be targeted at a specific challenge, or opportunity with clear actionable goals and community-validated criteria for evaluating its impact.

6. The strategy will support high-quality, trustworthy, and verifiable data

High-quality, verifiable data and metadata enable more insightful analysis, improves trust through reliability, and anchors data to its creators, increasing the interoperability and integrity of information across systems. The PID strategy will prioritize systems that foster trust and enhance the quality of PIDs and their metadata, while respecting the security and privacy of individual researchers and contributors.

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